

CHECKLIST OF FUNGAL SPECIES ASSOCIATED WITH SAFFRON PLANTS (*CROCUS SATIVUS* L.)

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Abstract

Over the past years, a wealth of studies has shown that saffron plants (*Iridaceae*) are subjected to intense fungal colonisation. Saffron (*Crocus sativus*) are perennial, monocotyledonous plants mainly restricted to the temperate areas and represents an economically important crop producing the world's costliest spice. The inventory of fungi associated with saffron is an essential step to explore the fungal diversity and fill the gaps in knowledge of diverse and understudied assemblage related to saffron. In this regard, the data collected from the literature for the diversity of saffron fungi have been revisited and updated here to realize a first inventory list on fungal organisms globally reported. It includes 137 species belonging to four phylums Ascomycota, Basidiomycota, Mucoromycota and Oomycota. *Fusarium* is the most common genus, with 26 species, followed by *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium*, with 15 and 17 species, respectively. The bulk of mycobiome often found in the cormosphere, roots, and rhizosphere suggest they might be involved in corms diseases development, however certain are known to be opportunists and others have a key role in corm protection. In conclusion, throughout this bibliographic inventory, we can point out a great diversity of fungi distinguishing the mycoflora of saffron that grow under appropriate environmental conditions and alerts us to the presence of several sources of infection in saffron fields for this perennial plant.

Keywords: Inventory, Endophytes, Fungi, Saffron, Morocco.

INTRODUCTION

Saffron is a species of crocus mainly growing in temperate and dry climatic conditions. However, its vegetative growth coincides with cold weather. We find it at altitudes varying by 50 m above sea level and more than 2000 m for the case of Morocco (Askaoune) Lage and Cantrell, 2009). A worldwide total yield of about 336 tons was produced on 105.269 hectares (Shokrpour, 2019). In 2019, Iran and Spain were the leading exporters of saffron (Fujii et al., 2022) and contributing about 88% of world's saffron, India (5.80%) followed by Greece, Afghanistan, Morocco, Italy, Spain, China and Azerbaijan. The biological and agronomical features of saffron make it an alternative plant for low-input agriculture, offering good production in sustainable agricultural systems and a source for earning in rural communities involved in its cultivation notably for marginal lands, especially where water scarcity severely limits the cultivation of many (Gresta et al., 2008).

Saffron is one of the most precious spices, derived from the dried stigmas of *Crocus sativus* flowers. The saffron plant belonging to the Iridaceae family, is a triploid geophyte species which is propagated only vegetatively by means of corms (Gresta

et al., 2008), the underground stems acting as storage and reproduction structures. Due to its numerous medicinal qualities and pharmacological applications, its demand and consumptions has risen over a period of time. Hence, new technologies will be required to improve and sustain its production. Efforts made to enhance the productivity in the traditional areas and promote the cultivation of saffron in the newer areas will be of great relevance towards achieving this goal if the knowledge on saffron ecosystems, including the potential biotique components as fungi is considered. In Morocco, as in other countries, serious interest in the study of endophytic, pathogenic and saprophytic fungal organisms on saffron crop has recently developed. Research on fungal communities gathered in saffron fields, soil, saffron plants and conducted in different saffron agroecosystems has resulted in the description of taxa that proved to be in some instances new, common on *Crocus sativus* or with restrict occurrence. The majority of studies emphasize on the fungal species affecting corms, being destructive in saffron and having caused severe yield losses in saffron producer's countries (Saeedizadeh, 2014; Palmero et al., 2014; Gupta et al., 2021; Vafaei and Darvishian, 2022; Ren et al., 2023; Caligiore-Gei et al., 2023; Khaledi et al., 2024). Numerous publications have recorded the mycobiota associated with saffron which includes endophytes, pathogenes and saprobes (Raj et al., 2013; Vardasbi et al., 2020; Belfiori et al., 2021). Advent in the methodology for the classification of fungi enables researchers to have more informations about fungi inhabiting living material and soil. High-throughput DNA sequencing techniques have greatly expanded the capability to characterize soil microbiome of saffron soil (Victorino et al., 2021).

Instead, in Morocco, the literature on saffron mycoflora is scarcer and there are four publications which have documented the fungal community of saffron plants and soils (Chamkhi et al., 2018; Bentata et al., 2017; El Aymani et al., 2019, Ourras et al., 2023).

El Aymani et al., (2019) compiled a list of 10 fungal species which were isolated from soil and infected plants. Bentata et al., (2017) have found 2 fungal species which were responsible for root rot disease or death. Recently, Ourras surveyed fungi from healthy or diseased corms and roots and isolated 18 fungal species accompagnied with indetermined fungal fraction. To complete the information, relevant literature was extensively reviewed for scattered records into a unified database. Thus, the present survey aims to collate fungi being reported to date on saffron (*Crocus sativus* L.) in Morocco and elsewhere.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Bibliographic Datasets

Data considered for the checklist of fungi of fungi recovered from saffron was based on primary literature (scientific publications in international journals with peer review process, books with ISBN number) and secondary literature (review papers, lists). These publications were found by searches, including Google Scholar, Google Connect, Lens.org. An update in taxonomy and systematics of recorded microfungi with their currently accepted name, author names of fungal genus and the corresponding family were achieved by using indexfungorum.org. The publications on reported microfungi across whorlwide were surveyed, with a focus on the terms such as 'corm rot', 'fungi', 'on', and 'saffron', '*Crocus sativus*'. The pathogenic nature and other life modes of individual fungal entities were then corroborated based on available literature. The search yielded various results: some articles had all the thematic

keywords and some were specific to fungal communities in association with saffron plants. Genera and species are listed alphabetically with extensive information and references.

Once species were checked for taxonomy in Index fungorum (<https://www.indexfungorum.org/names/Names.asp>, accessed on 05 June 2024).

Isolation and distribution of each species aspects were assessed by reviewing databases on fungal diversity and pathological studies on saffron plants.

RESULTS

The current list of saffron-fungi includes 137 fungal species referenced by 141 research works published since 1800 to 2024. The inventoried fungal species gathers fungal organisms isolated from healthy and infected saffron corms, organs of *Crocus sativus* in the most producing saffron countries reported by different paper researchs.

Phylum (Phylla) Ascomycota

Cl/Leotiomycetes

O/Helotiales

F/ Sclerotiniaceae

- *Botrytis* sp.

Isolation: corms

Location: Morocco, Netherlands

References: Ourras et al., 2023; Boerema and Hamers, 1989

- *Botrytis cinerea*

Isolation: leaves

Location : Italy

References : Belfiori et al., 2021

- *Botrytis fabiopsis*

Isolation: corms

Location: India

References: Wani et al., 2016, 2017

Sclerotinia

Sclerotinia gladioli

Isolation: saffron corm rot

Location: Japon

References: Abe, 1933; Yamamoto et al., 1954; Mizusawa, 1923);

Sclerotinia bulborum

Isolation: undeterminate

Location: Spain

References: Alarcon and Sanchez, 1968

Stromatinia gladioli

Isolation: infected leaf sheath, symptomatic corms

Location: Netherlands, Italy, Spain

References: Schenck 1970. Fiori et al., 2007; Muñoz et al., 2020

F/Ploettnerulaceae

Cadophora

Isolation: soil

Location: China

Reference: Lin et al., 2019

- *Cadophora luteo-olivacea*

Isolation: Corm

Location: Italy

References: Wani et al., 2016 ; Belfiori et al., 2023

- *Cadophora malorum*

Isolation: Roots, leaves, corms; corms

Location: India, Iran, Italy

References: Wani et al., 2016; Taheri et al., 2020; Belfiori et al., 2021

F/Myxotrichaceae

Oidiodendron

Isolation: rotting corms

Location: China

References: Ren et al., 2023

Cl/ Dothideomycetes

Pleosporales

F/Pleosporaceae

Alternaria

- *Alternaria* sp.

Isolation: Stems

Location: India

References: Raj, 2013

- *Alternaria alternata*

Isolation: leaves, corms, infected corms, stems, tepals and stigmas; Corms with some spots,

Location: Iran; Italy; Morocco, India

References: Hossainnia and Mohammadi, 2018; Vafaei and Darvishian, 2022; Belfiori et al., 2021; Ourras et al., 2023; Wani et al., 2016, 2017.

- *Alternaria chlamydosporigena*

Isolation: Roots

Location: Iran

References: Taheri et al. (2020)

- *Alternaria infectoria*

Isolation: tepals

Location: Italy

References: Belfiori et al. (2021).

Bipolaris

- *Bipolaris spicifera*

Isolation: corms

Location: Spain

References: Ahrazem et al., (2010); Rubio-Moraga et al., (2013)

- *Cochliobolus* sp.

Isolation: corms

Location : Spain

References : Ahrazem et al., (2010)

Pyrenophora

- *Pyrenophora tritici-repentis*

Isolation: tepals

Location: Italy

References: Belfiori et al., 2021);

Stemphylium

- *Stemphylium vesicarium*

Isolation: leaves

Location: Italy

References: Belfiori et al., (2021)

- *Stagonosporopsis cucurbitacearum*

Isolation : tepals

Location : Italy

References : Belfiori et al., (2021)

Ulocladium

- *Ulocladium* sp.,

Isolation: healthy corms

Location: Morocco

References: Ourras et al. (2023)

F/ Didymellaceae

G/Ascochyta

- *Ascochyta rabiei*

Isolation: leaves, corms and roots

Location: Iran

References: Taheri et al., (2020)

Epicoccum

- *Epicoccum* spp.

Isolation: rotten leaves of saffron plants

Location: Italy

References : Belfiori et al., (2021)

- *Epicoccum nigrum*

Isolation: rotten stem, saffron bulb

Location: Italy, India

References: Belfiori et al., 2021, Wani et al., 2016 ; Wani et al., 2017

G/Phoma

- *Phoma* spp.

Isolation: corms of saffron

Location: Netherlands; Spain, India, France, Italy, Romania,

References: Boerema, 1976; Pérez-Bueno, 1995; Lopez and Gomez-Gomez, 2009; Thakur et al., 1992; Hassan and Devi, 2003; Madan et al., 1967; Carta et al., 1982; Ionita et al., 1995.

- *Phoma crocophi*

Isolation: corm

Location: France, Italy, India, Romania

References: Madan et al., (1967); Nannizzi, 1941; Carta et al., 1982; Hassan and Devi, 2003; Ionita et al., 1995).

F/Didymosphaeriaceae

G/Paraphaeosphaeria

Isolation: Healthy and rotted corms

Location: China

References: Ren et al. (2023)

Cladosporiales

F/Cladosporiaceae

- *Cladosporium* sp.

Isolation: corms

Location: Spain

References: Ahrazem et al. (2010)

- *Cladosporium cladosporioides*

Isolation: leaves

Location: Italy

References: Belfiori et al., (2021)

Botryosphaeriales

F/Botryosphaeriaceae

Macrophomina

- *Macrophomina* sp.

Isolation: corms

Location: Italy, India, Iran, Romania

References: Razdan et al., (2018); Kumar (2018)

- *Macrophomina phaseolina*

Isolation: rotten corms

Location: Italy, India, Iran, Romania

References: Carta et al., 1982; Shah and Srivastava (1984); Sud et al., (1999); Gupta et al., (2011); Ionita et al., 1995 ; Gadiri et al., 2019.

Cl/Eurotiomycetes

O/Eurotiales

F/Trichocomaceae

Talaromyces

- *Talaromyces* sp.

Isolation: Corm

location: China

References: Du et al., (2023)

- *Talaromyces assiutensis*

Isolation: corms and leaves

Location: Italy

References: Belfiori et al. (2021)

- *T. aurantiacus*

Isolation : leaves, corms

location: Iran

References: Vardasbi et al., (2020)

- ***Talaromyces cecidicola***

Isolation: corms and stems

Location: Italy

References: Belfiori *et al.* (2021)

- ***Talaromyces cellulolyticus***

Isolation: corms

Location: India

References : Wani et al., (2016, 2017)

- ***T. funiculosus***

Isolation: leaves, corms

Location: Iran

References: Vardasbi et al., (2020)

- ***Talaromyces pinophilus***

Isolation: corms, leaves

Location: India, Italy, Iran

References: Wani et al., (2016, 2017); Belfiori et al., 2021 ; Vardasbi et al., (2020) **34**

- ***T. purpureogenus***

Isolation: Corms, leaves

Location: India, Iran

References : Wani et al., (2016); Vardasbi et al., (2020)

- ***Talaromyces verruculosus***

Isolation : Corms

Location: India

References: Wani et al., (2016, 2017)

- ***Talaromyces versatilis***

Isolation: Corms, leaves

Location: Iran

References: Vardasbi et al., (2020) [105]

F/Aspergillaceae

G/Aspergillus

***Aspergillus* sp.**

Isolation: roots; rotted corm

Location: Iran, China, India

References: Taheri et al., 2021; Xu and Ge, 1990; Gupta and Vakhlu, 2015; Kumar, 2018.

- *Aspergillus europaeus*

Isolation: stem of saffron

Location: Iran, Italy

References: Taheri et al., 2020 ; Belfiori et al., 2021

- *Aspergillus flavipes*

Isolation: infected saffron bulb

Location: Iran

References: (Najari et al., 2018, Saeedizadeh, 2014, Najjar et al., 2017)

- *Aspergillus flavus*

Isolation: diseased bulb

Location: Iran, India, Egypt

References: diseased bulbs in Iran (Najari et al., 2018, Saeedizadeh, 2014, Najjar et al., 2017), in India (Mansotra et al., 2023); Aziz et al., (1998);

- *Aspergillus fumigatiaffinis*

Isolation: roots isolated from roots of saffron in

Location: Morocco

Reference : Chamkhi et al. (2018)

- *Aspergillus fumugatis*

Isolation: saffron corms, roots and soil

Location: Morocco

References: El Aymani et al. (2019)

- *Aspergillus Niger*

Isolation: Dry styles, infected stem, corms, soil, asymptomatic corm and roots

Location: Egypt, Morocco, China, Spain, Iran

References: Aziz et al., (1998); Lahmess et al., (2021) ; El Aymani et al., 2019; Ourras et al., (2023), Ahrazam et al., (2010), Rubio-moraga et al., (2013); Xu and Ge (1990); Jiening et al., (2022); Najari et al., (2018); Saeedizadeh, (2014, 2016); Najjar et al., (2017); Taheri et al., (2020);

- *Aspergillus nomius*

Isolation: corms

Location: Morocco

References : Ourras et al., (2023)

- ***Aspergillus ochraceus***

Isolation: Corms

Location: Morocco

References (Ourras et al., 2023)

- ***Aspergillus oryzae***

Isolation: dry parts of styles and stigma

Location: Egypt

References: Aziz et al., (1998)

- ***Aspergillus parasiticus***

Isolation: Dry parts of styles and stigma

Location: Egypt

References: Aziz et al., (1998)

- ***Aspergillus pseudodeflectus***

Isolation: rotten corms

Location: India

References: Wani et al., (2016, 2017)

- ***Aspergillus terreus***

Isolation: diseased corms, root

Location: Iran, Egypt, Morocco

References: Saeedizadeh, (2014), Aziz et al., (1998), El Aymani et al., (2019)

- ***Aspergillus tamarii***

Isolation: dry parts of styles and stigma

Location: Egypt

References: Aziz et al., (1998)

- ***Aspergillus versicolor***

Isolation : Corms

Location : Morocco

References: Ourras et al., (2023)

G/Paecilomyces

- ***Paecilomyces marquandii***

Isolation: rotten bulbs

Location: India

References: Wani et al., (2016, 2017)

G/Penicillium

- ***Penicillium sp.***

Isolation: diseased bulbs, stems, roots, soil,

Location: Italy; France; India, Spain, Morocco, China

References: Saaltink, 1971; Carta et al., 1982; Madan et al., 1967; Kumar, 2018; Gupta and Vakhlu; Raj, 2013; Thakur et al., 1992; Hassan and Devi, 2003; Hassan et al., 2003; Wani, 2004; Ahmed and Sagar, 2006; Husaini et al., 2010; Shah et al., 2018; Razdan et al., 2018; Ahrazem et al., 2010; El Aymani et al., 2019; Ourras et al., 2023; Xu and Ge, 1990; Du et al., 2023.

- ***Penicillium canescens***

Isolation: leaves, corms, roots

Location: Iran, India

References: Taheri et al., (2020), Wani et al., (2016, 2017)

- ***Penicillium chrysogenum***

Isolation: soil

Location: China

References: Shuwen et al., (2019)

- ***P. citreosulfuratum***

Isolation: rotted bulbs

Location: China

References: Tian et al., 2022; Hu et al., 2022

- ***Penicillium citrinum***

Isolation: rotten bulbs, stems

Location: China, Italy

References: Tian et al., 2022; Belfiori et al., 2021

- ***Penicillium corymbiferum***

Isolation: rotten corm

Location: Scotland, Italy, China, Japan, India

References: Sutton and Wale (1985); Capelli et al. (1991); Cappelli and Di Minco (1999); Saaltink (1971); Gu and Zhi (1997); Gupta et al. (2011).

- ***Penicillium crocicola***

Isolation: undetermined

Location: Japan

References: Yamamoto et al. (1956);

- ***Penicillium cyclopium***

Isolation: symptomatic corm

Location: Italy, China

References: Francesconi (1973); Picci (1986); Cappelli et al. (1991); Gu and Zhi (1997); Gu and Zhi (1997); Fiori (2002); Cappelli and Di Minco (1999).

- ***Penicillium digitatum***

Isolation: infected corms

Location: Italy, Iran

References: Carta et al. (1982); Saeedizadeh (2014, 2016); Najjar et al. (2017).

- ***Penicillium griseofulvum***

Isolation: corms

Location: India

References: Wani et al. (2016)

- ***Penicillium pinophilum***

Isolation: undeterminate

Location: India

References : Wani et al. (2016, 2017)

- ***Penicillium raistricki***

Isolation : infected saffron corm

Location : Morocco, Spain

References : Lamhass et al. (2021); Ahrazem et al. (2010); Rubio-Moraga et al. (2013).

- ***Penicillium solitum***

Isolation: diseased corm

Location: China

References: Zhang et al. (2020)

- ***Penicillium vinaceum***

Isolation: corm of saffron

Location: China

References: Zheng et al.(2012)

O/Onygenales

F/ Onygenaceae

- ***Malbranchea circinate***

Isolation :

Location : Italy

References: Belfiori et al., (2021)

O/Chaetothyriales

F/Herpotrichiellaceae

Phialophora

Isolation: Soil and bulb of saffron

Location: China

Reference: Lin et al. (2019)

Phialophora mustea

Isolation: Corm

Location: India

References: Raj (2013); Wani et al. (2016)

Cl/Sordariomycetes

Glomerellales

F/ Glomerellaceae

- ***Colletotrichum* sp.**

Isolation : soil

Location : India

References : Mansotra et al. (2023)

F/Plectosphaerellaceae

G/*Acrostalagmus*

- ***Acrostalagmus luteoalbus***

Isolation: soil

Location: Iran

References: Mohammadi and Amini (2015).

Incertae sedis

F/ Apiosporaceae

- ***Spegazzinia* sp.**

Isolation: stigmas

Location: Italy

Reference: Belfiori et al. (2021)

Hypocreales

F/Nectriaceae

G/*Fusarium*

- ***Fusarium* sp.**

Isolation: Stem, Soils, corms and roots of saffron plants

Location: China, India, Italy, China, Morocco

References: Xu and Ge (1990); Raj (2013); Hassan and Devi (2003); Hassan *et al.* (2003); Hussaini *et al.*, (2010); Farda *et al.* (2022); Mansotra *et al.* (2023); El Aymani *et al.* (2019).

- ***Fusarium acuminatum***

Isolation: infected corms

Location: Iran

References: Vafaei and Darvishian (2022).

- ***Fusarium avenaceum***

Isolation: symptomatic corms

Location: Morocco

References: Ourras *et al.* (2023).

- ***Fusarium bulbigenum*** Cke. And Mass var. *blasticola* (Rostr.)

Isolation: undetermined

Location: Japan

References: Yamamoto *et al.* (1954); Mizusawa (1923)

- ***Fusarium culmorum***

Isolation: soil, corm, roots, rotted corm

Location: Morocco, China, Iran

References: El Aymani *et al.*, (2019); Xu and Ge (1990); Khaledi *et al.* (2020)

- ***Fusarium fujikuroi***

Isolation: soil

Location: India

References: Mansotra *et al.* (2023)

- ***Fusarium moniliforme***

Isolation: undeterminate

Location: Spain, India, China

References: Ahrazem *et al.* (2010); Wani (2004); Mansotra *et al.* (2023)

- ***Fusarium moniliforme* var. *intermedium***

Isolation: rotten corm

Location: India

References: Dhar (1992); Sameer *et al.* (2018);

- ***Fusarium neocosmosporiellum***

Isolation: soil

Location: India

References: Mansotra *et al.*, (2023)

- *Fusarium oxysporum*

Isolation: diseased and rotten corms, roots, soil

Locations: India, Italy, Morocco, Spain, Iran, Argentina, China

References: Wani (2004); Kumar (2018); Gupta and Vakhlu (2015); Shah and Srivastava (1984); Kalha et al. (2007); Gupta et al. (2011); Sud et al. (1999); wani et al. (2016, 2017); Shah et al. (2018); Hassan Mir et al. (2011); Gupta et al. (2020); Gupta et al. (2021); Najari et al. (2018); Saeedizadeh (2014); Najjar et al. (2017); Vafaei and Darvishian (2022); Bhagat et al. (2022); Khaledi et al. (2020); Khaledi et al. (2024); Cappelli (1994); Palmero et al. (2014); Belfiori et al. (2021); Bentata et al. (2017); El Aymani et al. (2019); Lahmass et al. (2021); Ourras et al. (2023); Lopez and Gomez-Gomez (2009); Rubio-Moraga et al. (2013); Galvarez et al., (2014); Federico et al. (1997); Caligiore-Gei et al. (2023); Wei et al. (2021); Mirghasempour et al., (2022b); Tian et al. (2022); Ren et al. (2023); Luo et al. (2023)

- *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *saffrani*

Isolation: saffron bulbs

Location: Italy

References: Palmero et al. (2014);

- *Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp *croci*

Isolation: undetermined

Location: Netherlands

References: Boerema and Hamers (1988, 1989)

- *Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp *tuberosi*

Isolation: infected corms.

Location: Spain

References: Castillo and Gómez-Gómez (2009);

- *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *gläieuls*

Isolation: soil and roots, infected corms

Location: Italy; India, China

References: Di Primo et al. (2002); Shah and Srivastava (1984), Kalha et al. (2007), Gupta et al. (2011); Sud et al. (1999); Kumar (2018); Gupta and Vakhlu (2015); Xu and Ge (1990).

- *Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp *gladioli*

Isolation: on soil and roots.

Location: Netherlands, Japan, Germany, Italy; India

References: McClelland (1945); Yamamoto et al. (1954); Mes et al. (1994); Cappelli (1994); Capelli and Di Minco (1998); Di Primo and Cappelli (2000); Primo et al. (2002); Hassan Mir et al. (2011); Di Primo et al. (2002); Gupta et al. (2011);

- ***F. oxysporum f. sp. lycopersici***

Isolation : soil

Location : India

References : Mansotra et al. (2023)

- ***F. equiseti***

Isolation: rotten corms

Location: India, China

References: Shah et al. (2018); Wani (2004); Ahmed and Sagar (2006); Wei et al. (2021)

- ***F. pallidoroseum***

Isolation: rotten corms

Location: India

References: Wani (2004); Ahmed and Sagar (2006); Shah et al. (2018).

- ***Fusarium solani***

Isolation: infected corms, soil, corms, roots

Location: India, China, French; Italy; Spain;

References: Kumar (2018); Gupta and Vakhlu (2015); Gupta et al. (2011); Sud et al. (1999) ; Shah and Srivastava (1984); Hassan and Devi (2003); Kalha et al. (2007); Razdan et al. (2018); Ahmed and Sagar (2006); Wani (2004); Shah et al. (2018); Vafaei and Darvishian (2022); Hassan Mir et al. (2011); Mansotra et al. (2023); Tian et al. (2022); Madan et al. (1967); Rubio-Moraga et al. (2013).

- ***Fusarium roseum***

Isolation: isolated from rotten bulb; roots, soil

Location: China, Morocco

References: Xu and Ge (1990); El Aymani et al. (2019)

- ***Fusarium proliferatum***

Isolation : corm, root

Location : Iran

References : Khaledi et al. (2020)

- ***Fusarium culmorum***

Isolation: corm, root

Location: Iran

References: Khaledi et al. (2020);

- ***F. graminearum***

Isolation: corm, root

Location: Iran

References: Khaledi et al. (2020);

- ***Fusarium acuminatum***

Isolation: infected corms

Location: Iran

References: Vafaei and Darvishian (2022)

- ***Fusarium nirenbergiae***

Isolation: symptomatic corms tissues, rotted area on the corm

Location: China

References: Mirghasempour et al. (2022a);

- ***F. commune***

Isolation: root, rotten area of saffron corm

Location: China

References : Mirghasempour et al. (2022a,b)

- ***F. annulatum***

Isolation: root, symptomatic corms of *Crocus sativus*

Location: China

References: Mirghasempour et al. (2022a,b)

- ***Gibberella moniliformis***

Isolation: Soil

Location: India

Reference: Mansotra et al. (2023)

- ***Ilyonectria* sp.**

Isolation: Corm

Location : Italy

Reference : Belfiori et al. (2021)

- ***Ilyonectria macrodidyma***

Isolation: soil

Location : China

References : Shuwen et al. (2019)

- ***Fusicolla***

Isolation: rotting corms

Location: China

References: Ren et al. (2023)

Cl/Mortierellomycetes

O/Mortierellales

F/Mortierellaceae

Mortierella

- ***Mortierella alpina***

Isolation: soil

Location : India

References : Wani et al., 2016 ; 2017

- ***Mortierella humilis***

Isolation: soil

Location: China

References: Shuwen et al. (2019)

F/Hypocreaceae

G/Trichoderma

- ***Trichoderma sp.***

Isolation: corms, roots, soil, stem leaves

Location: China, Morocco, India, Italy

References: El Aymani et al. (2019); Ourras et al. (2023); Raj (2013) ; Belfiori et al. (2021).

- ***Trichoderma asperellum***

Isolation: saffron fields

Location: India

References: Gupta et al. (2020)

- ***Trichoderma harzianum***

Isolation : soil

Location : China

References : Mansotra et al. (2023)

F/Cordycipitaceae

Beauveria

- ***Beauveria sp.***

Isolation: Healthy corm, infected corms

Location: Spain, Morocco

References: Ahrazem et al. (2010); Ourras et al. (2023); Lo´pez and Go´mez-Go´mez (2009)

Parengyodontium

- ***Parengyodontium album***

Isolation: corm

Location: Italy

References: Belfiori et al. (2021)

Acremonium

- ***Acremonium sp.***

Isolation: Healthy corms

Location: Morocco

Reference: Ourras et al. (2023)

- ***Acremonium alternatum***

Isolation: Infected corms

Location: India

References: Wani et al. (2016; 2017).

O/Microascales

F/Microascaceae

Graphium

Isolation: Healthy and rotted corms

Location: China

References: Ren et al. (2023)

O/Sordariales

F/Chaetomiaceae

Ovatospora

- ***Ovatospora brasiliensis***

Isolation: stigmas

Location: Italy

Reference: Belfiori et al. (2021)

- ***Humicola***

Isolation: Rotted corm

Location: China

Reference : Ren et al. (2023)

Cl/ Saccharomycetes

O/Saccharomycetales

F/Dipodascaceae

Geotrichum

- ***Geotrichum candidum***

Isolation: soil

Location: India

References: Mansotra et al. (2023)

F/ Debaryomycetaceae,

- ***Meyerozyma caribbica***

Isolation: Corm, stem

Location: Italy

References: Belfiori et al. (2021)

Phylum: MUCOROMYCOTA

Cl/Mucoromycetes

O/Mucorales

F/Mucoraceae

Mucor

- ***Mucor* sp.**

Isolation: corm

Location: India

References: Shah et al. (2018); Wani (2004); Ahmed and Sagar (2006)

- ***Mucor fragilis***

Isolation : tepals, stigmas

Location : Italy

References: Belfiori et al. (2021)

- ***Mucor circinelloides***

Isolation: corms, soil

Location: Italy, India

References: Belfiori et al. (2021); Mansotra et al. (2023).

F/ Rhizopodaceae

Rhizopus

- ***Rhizopus nigricans***

Isolation: infectd corm

Location: Spain, Morocco

References: Ahrazem et al. (2010); Rubio-Moraga et al. (2013); Lamhass et al. (2021).

- ***Rhizopus oryzae***

Isolation: rotted saffron bulb, soil, corms and roots; stem and leaves.

Location: China, Morocco; Italy

References: Xu and Ge (1990); El Aymani et al. (2019); Chamkhi et al. (2018); Ourras et al. (2023), Belfiori et al. (2021);

- *Rhizopus stolonifer*

Isolation: Infected saffron

Location: Iran

References: Najari al. (2018); Saeedizadeh (2014, 2016)

Cl/Mortierellomycetes

O/Mortierellales

F/Mortierellaceae

Mortierella

- *Mortierella alpina*

Isolation: soil

Location : India

References : Wani et al. (2016, 2017)

- *Mortierella humilis*

Isolation: soil

Location : China

References : Shuwen et al. (2019)

Cl/ Orbiliomycetes

O/ Orbiliales

F/ Orbiliaceae

- *Monacrosporium* sp.

Isolation: on soil and roots.

Location: Morocco

References: Bentata et al. (2017)

Phylum Basidiomycota

Cl/Agaricomycetes

O/Agaricales

F/ Typhulaceae

Sclerotium

- *Sclerotium crocophilum*

Isolation: indeterminate

Location: France

Reference: Bastiou (1872)

- ***Sclerotium rolfsii***

Isolation: rotten corm

Location: India

References: Kalha *et al.* (2007); Shah *et al.* (1984); Gupta *et al.* (2011); Sud *et al.* (1999); Razdan *et al.* (2018)

O/ Cantharellales

F/ Strophariaceae

Rhizoctonia

- ***Rhizoctonia sp.***

Isolation: stem, corm, diseased saffron bulb

Location: India, France; Italy; Romania

References : Razdan *et al.* (2018); Wani *et al.* (2016); Kumar (2018); Gupta and Vakhlu (2015), Raj (2013); Thakur *et al.* (1992); Hassan and Devi (2003); Shah *et al.* (1984); Madan *et al.* (1967); Carta *et al.* (1982); Ionita *et al.* (1995).

- ***Rhizoctonia solani***

Isolation: undetermined

Location: southern France, India

References: Duhamel (1728), Hassam Mir *et al.* (2011);

- ***Rhizoctonia crocorum***

Isolation: roots, corm

Location: France, Italy, Spain, Romania, India, Greece

References: Alarcon and Sanchez (1968); Bastiou (1972); Madan *et al.* (1967); Carta *et al.* (1982); Ionita *et al.* (1995); Thakur *et al.* (1992); Hassan and Devi (2003).

- ***Rhizoctonia violacea***

Isolation: soil, corms

Location: France, Italy, Spain, Morocco

References: Bastiou (1872); Voglino (1905); Nannizzi (1941); Pérez-Bueno (1995); De Andrés (1998); Bentata *et al.* (2017).

- ***Rhizoctonia violacea var. crocorum***

Isolation: undetermined

Location: Italy

References: Nannizzi (1941)

Phylum : Oomycota

Cl /Peronosporae

O/Peronosporales

F/Pythiaceae

Pythium

- *Pythium* spp.

Isolation: rotten saffron bulbs

Location: Netherlands, France, Italy, India, Romania

References: Schenk (1969); Madan et al. (1967); Carta et al. (1982); Thakur et al. (1992); Hassan and Devi (2003); Ionita et al. (1995).

- *Phytium irregular*

Isolation: root

Location: Netherlands

Reference: Van Os et al. (998)

F/Peronosporaceae

- *Phytophthora* sp.

Isolation: saffron stems and corm

Location: India

References: Raj (2013); Hassan Mir et al. (2011)

DISCUSSION

The check-list includes the names, isolation source, location and references of about 130 microfungi that are assigned to 18 orders within 11 Classes (Eurotiomycetes, Leotiomycetes, Dothideomycetes, Mucoromycetes, Mortierellomycetes, Agaricomycetes, Saccharomycetes, Tremellomycetes, Orbiliomycetes, and Peronosporales) and 4 phyla (Ascomycota, Mucoromycota, Basidiomycota, and Oomycota).

The Ascomycota is represented by 72 species divided into 34 genera and 21 families. Within the Ascomycota, at the order level, Eurotiales had the greatest number of species (42 species) followed by Hypocreales (39 species) and the most dominant genera were *Fusarium*, *Penicillium* (16 species) and *Aspergillus* (15 species). Based on the number of species, *Fusarium* genus should rank first, it displays a great richness with 30 species.

Through concerted endeavors of mycologists and plant pathologists, past surveys on phytopathogenic fungal identification and diagnosis of saffron disease have served as the basis of reviews considered as a mini and specified list of saffron-colonizing fungal organisms (Gupta et al., 2011; 2021) listing more than 23 species associated with diseased saffron plants. Within the category of plant pathogenic fungi, the fusarioid species like *F. nirenbergiae*, *F. annulatum*, and *F. commune* (Mirghasempour et al., 2022a) as well as *F. avenaceum* (Ourras et al., 2023) were newly introduced in existing databases as for *P. solitum*, encountered in China and recognized as new pathogens on saffron plants (Zhang et al., 2020).

New taxa from Iran were also inventoried among the saffron-cormosphere mycobiota such as *Talaromyces versatilis*, *T. aurantiacus* (Vardasbi et al., 2020) and

Talaromyces cecidicola in Italy by Belfiori et al., (2021). Mycological contributions of Taheri et al., (2020) conducted on saffron in Hamadan province have characterized 7 endophytic species belonged to the Ascomycota group among them *Aspergillus europaeus* which was retrieved for the first time from this host in Iran and in the world. Opposing the fact that *A. europaeus* is commonly known as soil inhabiting fungi, the research work of Belfiori et al., 2021 approved the findings of Taheri related to *A. europaeus*. The *Aspergillus* genus's noteworthy representation on saffron corm, rhizospheric soil was assigned by 15 species following *Penicillium* genus with 14 species

Moreover, it is worthy the biodiversity of soil mycobiota in saffron grown fields given the limited number of taxa listed. In Morocco, members of 5 genera including *Fusarium*, *Penicillium*, *Trichoderma*, *Rhizopus* and *Aspergillus* were isolated (El Aymani et al., 2019). Along this checklist, a few species are the outcome of studies conducted by Mansotra et al. (2023) who report 12 species among them four fusarioid species (*F. oxysporum*, *F. solani*, *F. fujikuroi*, *F. neocosmosporiellum* and *Fusarium* sp.), *Trichoderma* sp., *T. harzianum* and *Colletotrichum*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Geotrichum candidum*, *Mucor circinelloides*, *Gibberella moniliformis*, and *Fusarium* sp., This indicates that there are numerous gaps in describing fungal diversity in soil saffron fields. In comparison, we can talk about compositional differences of soil mycobiota endorsed by Victorino et al., (2021) who have used metagenomic analysis to explore the soil fungal communities associated with alpine field-grown Saffron (*Crocus sativus* L.). These authors determined other taxa at the level genus *Fusicolla*, *Blumeria*, *Colletotrichum*, *Curvularia*, *Gibberella*, *Leptosphaeria*, *Plectosphaerella*, *Ramularia*, *Stigmina*.

CONCLUSION

This document constitute the first inventory of fungal species inhabiting saffron rhizosphere, soil and plant parts of *Crocus sativus* on which some cause plant diseases. The current checklist can be used as a reference by mycologists to retrieve fungal species from existing culture banks in Morocco and aboard mentioned on the website. The study highlighted *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium* and *Fusarium* spp as major candidates for infesting corms and vegetatif parts of saffron. These species are considered to be the most prolific mycotoxigenic species (Bennett and Klich, 2003). This data provided in the Checklist will be useful in the compilation of fungal biodiversity on saffron agrosystem. But, the checklist will, not by any means, be a conclusive list and new records will continue to be added regularly in the future.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

References

- 1) Abe, T., (1933). Studies on a new dry rot disease of the bulb of *Crocus sativus* L. caused by *Fusarium bulbigenum* Cke. et Mass var. *blasticola* (Rostr.) Wr. Trans. Tottori Soc". Agric. Sci., 4, pp. 212–228, 1933.
- 2) Abouddrar, A. (2009). Guide de bonnes pratiques agronomiques du safran, Rapport de consultation, Maroc: Projet FAO/TCP/MOR/3201, 2009, <http://www.foodquality-origin.org/documents/morocco/FAOTCPMOR3201-2a.pdf>. Visité le 10 décembre 2014.
- 3) Ahmad, T., Bashir, A., Farooq, S., Riyaz-UI-Hassan, S., (2022). *Burkholderia gladioli* E39CS3, an endophyte of *Crocus sativus* Linn. Induces host resistance against corm-rot caused by *Fusarium oxysporum*. J. Appl. Microbiol., 132, pp. 495–508. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jam.15190>
- 4) Ahmed, M. and Sagar, V. (2006). Annual progress report on 'integrated management of corm/tuber rot of saffron and kalazeera" (Horticulture Technology Mission-1 project 2.2), p 10, 2006.
- 5) Ahrazem, O., Rubio-Moraga, Á., Castillo-Lopez, R., Trapero, A., Gómez-Gómez, L. (2010). *Crocus sativus* pathogens and defense responses". Funct. Plant Sci. Biotechnol. 4(2), pp. 81–90.
- 6) Alarcon, J., and Sanchez, Y. A., Elazafranhejadivulgadora, (1968). In the saffron disclosing Sheet; Ministry of Agriculture: Madrid, Spain, p. 68. (In Spanish)
- 7) Ali, T., Bhagat, N., Magotra, S., and Vakhlu, J. (2024). Plant growth promotion and induction of defense response in *Crocus sativus* L. by two native *Bacillus* species against *Fusarium oxysporum* R1. J Plant Growth Regul **43**, pp. 787–806, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00344-023-11139-0>
- 8) Aziz, N. H., Youssef, A. Youssef, Y.A., El-Fouly, M.Z., Moussa, L.A. (1998). Contamination of some common medicinal plant samples and spices by fungi and their mycotoxins". Botanical Bulletin of Academia Sinica, 39, pp. 279-285.
- 9) Barnes, S.E. and Shaw, M.W. (2003). Infection of commercial hybrid primula seed by *Botrytis cinerea* and latent disease spread through the plants". Phytopathology, 93, pp. 573–578.
- 10) Bashir, S., Mughal, M.N., Nehvi, F.A., Dar, S. A., un nissa, S., Dar, Z. A., Hakeem, S. A., Wani, R. A., Baba, J.A., and Habib, M. (2017). Identification of sources of resistance in Saffron (*Crocus sativus* L.) to *Fusarium oxysporum* causing corm rot disease. Int. J. Curr. Microbiol. App. Sci 6(11), pp. 3660-3665.
- 11) Bastiou, P. (1872). Monographie du safran. Paris. 40 p.
- 12) Belfiori, B., Rubini, A., and Riccioni, C. (2021). Diversity of endophytic and pathogenic fungi of saffron (*Crocus sativus*) plants from cultivation sites in Italy". Diversity, 13, pp. 535. <https://doi.org/10.3390/d13110535>
- 13) Bentata, F., Lage, M., Bakhy, K., Ibrahim, M., Jbair, A., El Aissami, A., Kissayi, K.H., and Labhilili, M. (2017). Sanitary assessment of saffron corms and soil from Great Moroccan production areas: Taliouine and Taznakht". Acta Hort. 1184, pp. 263-266. DOI: 10.17660/ActaHortic.2017.1184.37
- 14) Bhagat, N., Magotra, S., Gupta, R., Sharma, S., Verma, S., Verma, P. K., Ali, T., Shree, A. and Vakhlu, J. (2022a). Invasion and colonization of pathogenic *Fusarium oxysporum* R1 in *Crocus sativus* L. during corm rot disease progression. J. Fungi, 8, pp. 1246. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jof8121246>
- 15) Bhagat, N., Mansotra, R., Patel, K., Ambardar, S., Vakhlu J. (2024). Molecular warfare between pathogenic *Fusarium oxysporum* R1 and host *Crocus sativus* L. unraveled by dual transcriptomics. Plant Cell Rep **43**, 42. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00299-023-03101-x>
- 16) Bhagat, N., Mansotra, R., Patel, K. And Vakhlu, J. (2022b). Saffron-Fusarium oxysporum R1 dual transcriptomics unravels, defense mechanism of saffron and robust pathogenicity of *Fusarium oxysporum* R1. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2132821/v1>
- 17) Boerema, G. H., and Hamers M. E., (1989). Check-list for scientific names of common parasitic fungi. Series 3b: Fungi on bulbs: Amaryllidaceae and Iridaceae". Neth. J. Plant Pathol., 95(3), pp. 1–29.

- 18) Boerema, G. H. and Hamers, M. E. (1988). Check-list for scientific names of common parasitic fungi. Series 3b: Fungi on bulbs: Liliaceae. Netherl. J. Plant Pathol. 94(suppl.), pp. 1-32.
- 19) Boerema, G.H. (1976). The Phoma species studies in culture by Rd RWG Dennis. Transactions of the British Mycology Society 67, pp. 289-319.
- 20) Boerema, G.H., and van Kesteren, H.A. (1956). The underground attacks on Crocus and Colchicum by the rusts *Uromyces croci* and *Uromyces colchici* respectively. European Journal of Plant Pathology 71, pp.136-144.
- 21) Caligiore-Gei, P.F., Moratalla-López, N., Poggi, L.M., Alonso, G.L. (2023). Isolation, identification, and determination of the virulence of the causal agents of corm rot of saffron (*Crocus sativus* L.) in Valle de Uco, Argentina. Plants, 12, pp. 2717, <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants12142717>
- 22) Cappelli, C., Buonauro, R., Polverari, A. (1991). Occurrence of *Penicillium corymbiferum* on saffron in Italy. Plant Pathology, 40(1), pp. 148–149, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-3059.1991.tb02304.x>
- 23) Cappelli, C., Di Minco, G. (1998). Control of *Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp. *gladioli* based on the production of pathogen free saffron corms. Journal of Plant Pathology, 80 (3), Sixth SIPaV Annual Meeting, 253.
- 24) Cappelli, C., and Di Minco, G. (1999). Three-years of trials on saffron diseases in Abruzzo (Central Italy) [*Crocus sativus* L.]". Inf Fitopatologia 49.
- 25) Cappelli, C. (1994). Occurrence of *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *gladioli* on saffron in Italy. Phyto. Medi, 33, pp. 93–94.
- 26) Carta, C., Flori, M., and Franceschini, A. (1982). Charcoal rot of saffron (*Crocus sativus* L.) Bulbs. Istituto di PatologiaVegatale dell University di Sassari Italy: 2929, pp. 193–197.
- 27) Castillo, R., and Gomez-Gomez, L. (2009). Isolation of a new fungi and wound-induced chitinase class in corms of *Crocus sativus*. Plant Physiology and Biochemistry 47, pp. 426-434.
- 28) Chamkhi, I., Sbabou, L., Aurag, J. " Endophytic fungi isolated from *Crocus sativus* L.(saffron) as a source of bioactive secondary metabolites". Pharmacognosy Journal, 10, pp. 1143-1148, 2018, DOI:10.5530/pj.2018.6.195
- 29) Compant, S., Saikkonen, K., Mitter, B., Campisano, A., Mercado-Blanco, J. (2016). Editorial special issue: soil, plants and endophytes. Plant Soil 405(1), pp. 1–11.
- 30) de Andrade, G.A.K., Bezerra, J.D.P., de Vargas, M.V.M., Bernardes, B.M., Goulart, S.N.B., Alves, R.P., Küster, M.C.T., Pereira, A.B., Victoria, F.D.C. (2022). Endophytic fungi from an overlooked plant species: A case study in *Kelissa brasiliensis* (Baker) Ravenna. Acta Botanica Brasilica, 36: e2020abb0426.
- 31) De Andrés, M. F., Garcia-Arenal, F., Lopez, M.M., Melgarejo, P. (1998). Patogenos de plantas descritos en Eqpana, Coed. Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentacion. Sociedad Espanola de Fitopatologia, Madrid, 526 pp.,
- 32) del Gallo, M., Farda, B., Djebaili, R., Sabbi, E., Ercole, C., Pace, L., Pellegrini, M. (2023). Microbial communities investigation and biocontrol activity in saffron cultures", EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-16433, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-16433>, 2023.
- 33) Dhar, A. K. 1992. Bio-ecology and control of corm rot of saffron (*Crocus sativa* L). Master's thesis Division of Plant Pathology, SKUAST-K (J &K) p109.
- 34) Di Primo, P., Cappelli, and C., Katan, T. (2002). Vegetative compatibility grouping of *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *gladioli* from saffron". Eur. J. Plant Pathol, 108, pp. 869–875.
- 35) Di Primo, P., Cappelli, C. (2000). Preliminary characterization of *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *gladioli* causing Fusarium corm rot of saffron in Italy. Plant Disease, 84(7), pp. 806. <https://eurekamag.com/research/066/555/066555431.php>
- 36) Douglas, M.H., Smallfield, B.M., Wallace, A.R., McGimpsey, J.A. (2014). Saffron (*Crocus sativus* L.): The effect of mother corm size on progeny multiplication, flower and stigma production". Scientia Horticulturae 166, pp. 50–58, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.scienta.2013.12.007>

- 37) Du, S., Lu, J., Hu, B. Han, T., Kong, Z., Qin, L. and Zhu, B. (2023). Endophytic Fungi Prevent Corm Rot Disease and Stimulate the Growth and Metabolism of *Crocus sativus*. *Appl Biochem Microbiol* **59**, 503–510. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S0003683823040038>
- 38) Duggar, B. M. (1915). *Rhizoctonia crocorum* (Pers.) DC. And *R. solani* Kuhn (*Corticium Vagum* B. & C.)", *Annals of the Missouri Botanical Garden* 2(3), pp. 403-458, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/2990113>.
- 39) Duhamel, H. L., 1728. Explication physique d'une maladie qui fait perir plusieurs plantes dans le Gatinois et particulièrement le safran. *Hist. Acad. Roy. Sci. Paris*, 100-112.
- 40) Duran, P., Thiergart, T., Garrido-Oter, R., Agler, M., Kemen, E., Schulze-Lefert, P., Hacquard, S. (2018). Microbial interkingdom interactions in roots promote Arabidopsis survival". *Cells* 175, pp. 973–983.e14, doi: 10.1016/j.cell.2018.10.020
- 41) Edel-Hermann V., Lecomte C., "Current status of *Fusarium oxysporum* formae speciales and races". *Phytopathology* 109, pp. 512–530, 2019. Doi: 10.1094/PHYTO-08-18-0320-RVW.
- 42) El Aymani I., Qostal S., Mouden N., Selmaoui K., Ouazzani Touhami A., Benkirane R. And A. Douira A. "Fungi associated with saffron (*Crocus sativus*) in Morocco" *Plant Cell Biotechnology and Molecular Biology* 20 (23&24), pp. 1180–1188, 2019, <https://ikprress.org/index.php/PCBMB/article/view/4840>
- 43) Farda B., Djebaili R., Bernardi M., Pace L., Del Gallo M., Pellegrini M., "Bacterial microbiota and soil fertility of *Crocus sativus* L. rhizosphere in the presence and absence of *Fusarium* spp. ", *Land*, 11(11), pp. 2048-2048, 2022.
- 44) Federico A., Onis A., Pelaez M., Vinagre D., Pedraza V., Della Maggiora A., Ridao A.d.C., Flego D., "Determinación de *Fusarium oxysporum* afectando azafrán en el sudeste de la provincia de Buenos Aires, Argentina". In *Proceedings of the Congreso Latinoamericano de Fitopatología*, Montevideo, Uruguay, 12–17 October, 203, 1997.
- 45) Fiori M., "Avversità. In: Zafferano. Storia, Cultura, Coltivazione e Impiego a San Gavino Monreale e in Sardegna. (F. Sanna, ed.) E.R.S.A.T. Centro Zonale di Guspini. Medio Campidano, Sardinia, Italy, pp. 68–73, 2002.
- 46) Fiori M., G., Falchi Quagliaand M., Cappelli C., "Saffron (*Crocus sativus* L.) diseases in Italy". In: *Atti Del XIV Congresso Nazionale SIPaV*. Perugia 18–21 Settembre 2007, *Journal of Plant Pathology* 89 (3, special issue), 55., 2007.
- 47) Fiori M., Ligios V., Schiaffino A. "Identification and characterization of Burkholderia isolates obtained from bacterial rot of saffron (*Crocus sativus* L.) grown in Italy", *Phytopathologia Medit.* 50, pp. 450-461, 2011, https://doi.org/10.14601/Phytopathol_Mediterr-8730
- 48) Francesconi A., "the rotting of bulbs of *Crocus sativus* L. by *Penicillium cyclopium* Westling". *Ann. Di Bot*, 32, pp. 63–70, 1973.
- 49) Fujii S., Morita Y., Ohta T., Uto- T., Shoya Y., "Saffron (*Crocus sativus* L.) as a valuable spice and food product: a narrative review". *Longhua Chin Med*, 5(18), pp. 1-12, 2022, doi: 10.21037/lcm-22-1
- 50) Gadiri Z., Tarighi S., "Effect of endophyte bacteria on biocontrol of *Macrophomina phaseolina*, the causal agent of charcoal decay of saffron corm". 4th Iranian Mycological Congress, 26-28 August, Sari Agricultural Sciences and Natural Resources University, Iran. pp.136, 2019.
- 51) Gálvez L., Abato C., García-Díaz M., Benito S., Gómez-Gómez L., Ahrazem O., Palmero D., "Study of the etiology of corm rot of saffron (*Crocus sativus* L.) in Castilla La-Mancha (Spain) and parasitic specificity of the causative agent". VII Congreso Ibérico de Agroingeniería y Ciencias Hortícolas: innovar y producir para el futuro. Libro de actas / coord. by Francisco Ayuga Téllez, Alberto Masaguer, Ignacio Mariscal Sancho, Morris Villarroel Robinson, Margarita Ruiz Altisent, Fernando Riquelme Ballesteros, E. C. Correa, pages 346-351. 2014
- 52) Gao S., Sun W. S., Yu C. L., Li L., Zhang T. J., 2021: Analysis of soil fungal community structure in gentiana rhizosphere based on high-throughput sequencing. *Jiangsu Agric. Sci.* 49, pp.190–195, 2021, doi: 10.15889/j.issn.1002-1302.2021.12.032.

- 53) García-Jiménez J., Alfaro-García A., "Fusarium oxysporum Schlecht. As causal agent of a seedborne disease of Saffron (*Crocus sativus* L.). 7th Congress of the Mediterranean Phytopathological Union, Granada, Spain, pp. 156, 1987.
- 54) Goliaris A.H."Saffron cultivation in Greece". In: Negbi M (Ed) Saffron (*Crocus sativus* L.), Harwood Academy Publishers, Australia, pp. 73-85, 1999.
- 55) Gresta F., Lombardo G. M., Siracusa L., Ruberto G., "Effect of mother corm dimension and sowing time on stigma yield, daughter corms and qualitative aspects of saffron (*Crocus sativus* L.) in a Mediterranean environment". J Sci Food Agr. 88(7), pp. 1144–1150. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsfa.3177>.
- 56) Gu, Z.F. Zhi, Y., "A study on biological characteristics of *Penicillium corymbiferum* on crocus". Acta Agriculturae Shanghai, 13 (4), pp. 71–74, 1997.
- 57) Gufeng Q., Tingdan R., Qiang W., Chuanqing Z., "Bioactivity of mefentrifluconazole against *Fusarium oxysporum* causing saffron corm rot". Chinese Journal of Pesticide, 25(4), pp. 850-857, 2023. DOI: 10.16801/j.issn.1008-7303.2023.0033
- 58) Gugnani H.C."Ecology and Taxonomy of pathogenic Aspergilli". Frontiers Biosci. 8: pp. 346-357, 2003.
- 59) Guo J., Shi G., Kalil A., Friskop A., Elias, E., Xu, S. S., Faris J. D., Liu Z., "Pyrenophora tritici-repentis Race 4 Isolates cause disease on Tetraploid Wheat". Phytopathology, 110:11, pp.1781-1790, 2020.
- 60) Gupta R., Vakhlu J., " Native *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* W2 as a potential biocontrol for *Fusarium oxysporum* R1 causing corm rot of *Crocus sativus*". Eur. J. Plant Pathol. 143, pp.123–131, 2015. Doi: 10.1007/s10658-015-0670-3.
- 61) Gupta V., Kalha C. S., Razdan Dolly V. K., " Etiology and Management of corm rot of saffron in Kishtwar District of Jammu and Kashmir, India". J Mycol Plant Pathol, 41(3), pp. 361-366, 2011.
- 62) Gupta V., Kumar K., Fatima K., Razdan V.K., Sharma B. C., Mahajan V., Pradeep Rai K., Sharma A., Gupta V., Hassan M.G., Hussain R., " Role of biocontrol agents in management of corm rot of saffron caused by *Fusarium oxysporum*". Agronomy, 10, pp.1398, 2020, doi: 10.3390/agronomy10091398.
- 63) Gupta V., Sharma A., Rai P.K., Gupta S.K., Singh B., Sharma S.K., Singh S.K., Hussain R., Razdan V.K., Kumar D., et al. "Corm Rot of Saffron: Epidemiology and Management". Agronomy, 11, pp. 339, 2021. <https://doi.org/>
- 64) Hassan M.G., Devi L.S., " Corm rot diseases of saffron in Kashmir valley". Indian Phytopathol., 56, pp.122, 2003.
- 65) Hassan Mir G., Devi L. S., Ahmad S., Manoj Kumar V, Williams P., " Antagonistic potential of native isolates of *Trichoderma viride* on corm rot pathogen complex of saffron (*Crocus sativus*) in Kashmir. Plant pathology Journal, 10 (2), pp. 73-78, 2011.
- 66) Hassine M., Aydi B. A. R., Jabnoun K. H., Daami R. M., "Soil-borne and compost-borne *Penicillium* sp. and *Gliocladium* spp. as potential microbial biocontrol agents for the suppression of anthracnose-induced decay on tomato fruits". Egypt J Biol Pest Co. 32, pp. 1–12, 2022, doi: 10.1186/S41938-022-00519-5
- 67) Hossainnia A., Mohammadi A., " Investigation of *Alternaria alternata* pathogenicity on corm and leaves of saffron *in vitro* and greenhouse conditions". Saffron Agronomy & Technology 6 (1), pp. 61-72, 2018. DOI: 10.22048/jsat.2016.54452.116
- 68) Hu S., Sun W., Wang X., Wang L., Li W., 2021: First report of black spot caused by *Penicillium citreosulfuratum* on Saffron in Chongming Island, China. Plant Dis. 106(2),760. doi: 10.1094/PDIS-05-21-1038-PDN.
- 69) Husaini A. M., Jiménez A. J. L. Understanding saffron biology using omics-and bioinformatics tools: stepping towards a better Crocus phenome. Mol. Biol. Rep., pp. 1–16, 2022. doi: 10.1007/s11033-021-07053-x
- 70) Husaini A. M., Jiménez A. J. L. Understanding saffron biology using omics-and bioinformatics tools: stepping towards a better Crocus phenome. Mol. Biol. Rep., pp. 1–16, 2022. doi: 10.1007/s11033-021-07053-x

- 71) Husaini A.M., Kamili A.N., Wani M.H., Teixeira da Silva J.A., Bhat G.N., "Sustainable Saffron (*Crocus sativus* Kashmirianus) Production: Technological and Policy Interventions for Kashmir". *Functional Plant Science and Biotechnology*, 4 (2), pp.116-127, 2010.
- 72) Ionita A., Iliescu H., Jinga V., Iordache, E. *Macrophomina phaseolina* a dangerous parasite of cropped plants possibilities for control. *Probl. De Prot.* 1995, 23, 179–196.
- 73) Jan B., Reshi Z.A., Mohiddin F.A. Correction to: Site and Organ-Specific Culture-Dependent endophytic diversity of *Crocus sativus* L. (Saffron) in Kashmir Himalaya, India. *Microb. Ecol.* 2021.
- 74) Jiening W. Siqi G., Jiajia C., Xue D., Junbo L., Xiujian L., Guoyin K., Wei Z. Isolation and identification of pathogenic fungi of stem rot in *Crocus sativus* [J]. *Journal of Zhejiang A&F University*, 39(5): 1080-1086. 2022. Doi: 10.11833/j.issn.2095-0756.20210768.
- 75) Jin M., Yang C., Wang Y., Wei L., Osei R., 2023: Isolation and identification of *Epicoccum nigrum* as the causal agent of brown spot disease in *Solanum tuberosum* in China. *Plant Pathology*, 72, pp. 829–838, 2023. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1111/ppa.13696>
- 76) Kalha C.S., Gupta D., Priya S., First report of sclerotial rot of saffron caused by *Sclerotium rolfsii* in India. *Plant Disease*, 91, 9, pp.1203-1203, 2007.
- 77) Kalha C.S., Gupta V. Saffron 'a legendary crop' – an overview. *Plant Dis. Res.* 24: pp. 71–72, 2009.
- 78) Khaledi N. Evaluation of cell wall degrading enzymes of *Fusarium* species associated with root and corm of saffron in South Khorasan province. *Saffron Agronomy & Technology*, Vol. 8(2), pp. 243-259, 2020. DOI: 10.22048/jsat.2020.184121.1349.
- 79) Khaledi N., Rezaei M., and Alizadeh Farddarabad, M. Investigation into the Prevalence of *Fusarium* corm rot disease in saffron fields of Iran. *Saffron Agronomy & Technology*, 11(4), 393-412, 2024. DOI: 10.22048/jsat.2024.410910.1501
- 80) Khan, M.A., Naseer, S., Nagoo, S., Nehvi, F.A. Behaviour of saffron (*Crocus sativus* L.) corms for daughter corm production. *J. Phytol.* 3, 47–49, 2011.
- 81) Kumar K., 2018: Biological management of corm rot of saffron". (Master's Thesis). Sher-e-Kashmir University of Agricultural Sciences and Technology of Jammu, Main Campus, Chatha, Jammu. India. <https://krishikosh.egranth.ac.in/displaybitstream?Handle=1/5810062954>. [accessed 20 Dec 2020]
- 82) Kumar R., Singh V., Devi K., Sharma M., Singh, M. K., Ahuja, P. S. "State of art of Saffron (*Crocus sativus* L.) Agronomy: A comprehensive review", *Food Reviews International*, 25, pp. 44–85, 2009.
- 83) Lage M., Cantrell C. L., "Quantification of saffron (*Crocus sativus* L.) metabolites crocins, picrocrocin and safranal for quality determination of the spice grown under different environmental Moroccan conditions". *Scientia Horticulturae*, 121, pp. 366-373, 2009, <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:43553247>
- 84) Lahmass I., El Khoudri M., Ouahhoud S., Lahmass M., Khoulati A., Benyoussef S., Mamri S., Meziane M., Saalaoui E., "Biological effects and pharmacological activities of saffron of *Crocus sativus*". *Arabian Journal of Medicinal & Aromatic Plants*, 7 (2), pp. 254-268, 2021.
- 85) Lin Z., Liuyin Y., Youming C., Xue Z., Yongchun Z. 2019. Diversity analysis of microorganism in rhizosphere soil and bulbs of Chongming saffron (*Crocus sativus* L.). *Journal of Nuclear Agricultural Sciences*, 34(11):2452-2459.
- 86) Lo'pez R.C., Go'mez-Go'mez L., "Isolation of a new fungi and wound-induced chitinase class in corms of *Crocus sativus*". *Plant Physiology and Biochemistry*, 47, pp. 426–434, 2009.
- 87) Lu, J., Wang, J., Zhang, J. *et al.* Diversity of Culturable Endophytic Fungi in *Crocus sativus* and Their Correlation with Crocin Content. *Curr Microbiol* **80**, 73 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00284-023-03177-4>
- 88) Luo J., Zhang A., Tan, K., Yang, S., Ma, X., Bai X., Hou, Y., Bai J. " Study on the interaction mechanism between *Crocus sativus* and *Fusarium oxysporum* based on dual RNA-seq. *Plant cell reports*, 42, 1, pp. 91-106, 2022.

- 89) Madan C.L., Kapoor B.M., Gupta U.S., "Saffron. Economic Botany", 20, pp. 377-385, 1967.
- 90) Mansotra R., Ali T., Bhagat N. Vakhlu J., " Injury and not the pathogen is the primary cause of corm rot in *Crocus sativus* (saffron)". *Front. Plant Sci.* 14, pp.1074185, 2023. doi: 10.3389/fpls.2023.1074185
- 91) McClellan W.D., " Pathogenicity of the vascular *Fusarium* of *Gladiolus* to some additional iridaceous plants". *Phytopathology* 35, pp. 921–930, 1945.
- 92) Mirghasempour S.A., Studholme D.J., Chen W., Cui D., Mao B., "Identification and characterization of *Fusarium nirenbergiae* associated with saffron corm rot disease". *Plant Dis.*, 106, pp. 486–495, 2000a.
- 93) Mirghasempour S.A., Studholme D.J., Chen W., Zhu W., Mao B., " Molecular and pathogenic characterization of *Fusarium* species associated with corm rot disease in saffron from China". *J. Fungi*, 8, pp. 515, 2022b. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jof8050515>.
- 94) Mizusawa, Y. "A bacterial rot disease of saffron". *Ann. Phytopathol. Soc. Jpn.* 1, pp.1–12. 1923.
- 95) Mohammadi A, Amini Y., " Molecular Characterization and identification of *Acrostalagmus luteoalbus* from saffron in Iran". *Agriculture Science Developments*, 4, pp. 16-18, 2015.
- 96) Muñoz R. M., Lerma M.L., Castillo P., Armengol J., Somoza E., Woodhall J. W., " First report of *Stromatinia gladioli* causing neck and corm rot of *Crocus sativus* in Spain". *Plant Disease*, 104, 1, 282, 2020.
- 97) Najari G. H., Nourollahi K.H., Piri M., " The first report of (*Fusarium oxysporum*) causal agent of wild saffron corm rot disease in Iran". *Saffron Agron. Technol*, 6, pp. 119–123, 2018.
- 98) Najjar S., Mohammadi A., Asgari B., Mohammadi A.H. "Aflatoxin-producing *Aspergillus* species from saffron field soils in the South Khorasan province of Iran". *Arch. Phytopath. Plant Prot.* 50, pp. 349–360, 2017.
- 99) Nannizzi, A., " I parassiti delle piante officinali". Roma, Istituto Poligrafico dello Stato. pp. 1–544, 1941.
- 100) Os G.J.V., Gulik W.J.M.V., Boer W.J.D., " Disease development of *Pythium* root rot in bulbous *Iris* and *Crocus*". *Annals of Applied Biology*, 132, pp. 227-238, 1998. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-7348.1998.tb05199.x>
- 101) Ourras S., El Aymani I., Mouden N., Selmaoui K., Msairi S., Elouark M., Benkirane R., El Modafar C., Ouazzani Touhami A., Douira A., " Mycoflora of dormant *Crocus sativus* corms in Morocco". *J. Kacprzyk et al. (Eds.): AI2SD 2022, LNNS 713*, pp. 479–489. 2023, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-35248-5_43.
- 102) Palmero D., Rubio-Moraga A., Galvez-Paron L., Nogueras J., Abato C., Gomez-Gomez L., Ahrazem O. "Pathogenicity and genetic diversity of *Fusarium oxysporum* isolates from corms of *Crocus sativus*". *Ind. Crop. Prod.*, 61, pp. 186–192, 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2014.06.051>
- 103) Pérez-Bueno M., "El Azafran", Ediciones Agrotécnicas, Madrid, 228 pp., 1995.
- 104) Picci V., " Lo Zafferano *Crocus sativus* Linnaeus Coltivazione e preparazione della droga in Sardegna". *Annali Della Facoltà di Agraria dell'Università di Sassari. Studi Sassaresi Sezione III*, 32, pp. 15–31, 1985-86.
- 105) Ragukula K., Makandar R., " *Cladosporium cladosporioides* cause leaf blight on garden pea in Telangana, India". *Plant Disease*, pp. 2239, 2023.
- 106) Raj P., Khan S. S., Modak M., Lone Z.A., Rather S.A., Yaqoob M., " Biodiversity of endophytic fungi in saffron (*Crocus sativus*) and antimicrobial activity of their crude extract". *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 3, pp. 3702-3713, 2013.
- 107) Razdan V.K., Gupta V., Sharma A., "Transfer of integrated disease management technology for successful cultivation of saffron in Kishtwar district of J&K". *Acta Hort.* 1200, pp. 197-200, 2018, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.17660/ActaHortic.2018.1200.3283>. 85.
- 108) Ren T., Dai D., Yu M., Li T., Zhang C., "Identification and characterization of pathogens causing saffron corm rot in China". *Front. Microbiol.* 14, pp. 1188376, 2023. doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2023.1188376

- 109) Rubio-Moraga Á., Gómez-Gómez L., Trapero A., Castro-Díaz N., Ahrazem O., "Saffron corm as a natural source of fungicides: the role of saponins in the underground". *Ind. Crops Prod.* 49, pp. 915–921, 2013, doi:10.1016/j.indcrop.2013.06.029.
- 110) Saaltink G.J., "the infection of bulbs by *Penicillium* sp.", *Acta Hortic.*, 23, pp. 235–241, 1971.
- 111) Saeedizadeh A., " Identification of some saffron corm rot fungi and their control". *Saffron Agronomy & Technology*, 2 (3), pp. 213-205, 2014.
- 112) Saeedizadeh A., "Identification of some Saffron corm rot fungi and their control". *Saffron Agronomy & Technology. Supplement*, 4, pp. 37-37, 2016.
- 113) Sameer S.S., Bashir S., Nehvi F.A., Iqbal A.M., Naseer S., Nagoo S.A., Dar N.A., " Effect of biofertilizers, biological control agents and soil amendments on the control of saffron corm rot (*Crocus sativus* L.)". *Acta Hortic.* 1200, pp. 121-124, 2018, DOI: 10.17660/ActaHortic.2018.1200.20
<https://doi.org/10.17660/ActaHortic.2018.1200.20>
- 114) Schenk P.K., "Root rot in *Crocus*". *Netherland Journal of Plant pathology* 76, pp. 159-164, 1970.
- 115) Shah A., Srivastava K.K., "Control of corm rot of saffron". *Progress. Hortic.* 16, pp.141–143, 1984.
- 116) Shah M.U.D., Ahmad M., Sagar V., Padder B.A., Ahanger F.A., Sofi T.A., Nabi A.Mir., Kausar S. "In vitro evaluation of bioagents and fungitoxicants against *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Fusarium solani* causing corm rot of saffron (*Crocus sativus*) in Kashmir". *Acta Hortic*, 1200, pp.125–132, 2018.
- 117) Shokrpour M. *Saffron (Crocus sativus) breeding: opportunities and challenges*. Pages 675-706 in: *Advances in Plant breeding Strategies: Industrial and Food Crops*". J. Al-Khayri, S. Jain, and D. Johnson, eds. Springer, Cham, Switzerland, 2019.
- 118) Shuwen H., Qing Z., Jin L., Miao D., "Fungal diversity on the surface of saffron corms with different growth characteristics". *Plant Biosystems*, 155, pp. 302-309, 2021.
- 119) Shuwen H., Xi Y. Liqin L., Yumei Y., Guifen Z., Chong Y., Yan D., Xiaodong Q., " Limiting factors of saffron corm production from the perspective of microorganisms". *Sci. Hortic.*, 247, pp.165–174, 2019.
- 120) Sud A.K., Paul Y.S., Thakur B.R., "Corm rot of saffron and its management". *J. Mycol. Plant. Pathol*, 29, pp. 380–382, 1999.
- 121) Sutton M.W., Wale S.J., "the control of *Penicillium corymbiferum* on crocus and its effect on corm production". *Plant Pathol*, 34, pp. 566–570, 1985.
- 122) Taguiam, J.D., Evallo, E., Balendres, M.A."Epicoccum species: ubiquitous plant pathogens and effective biological control agents. *Eur J Plant Pathol.*, 159(4), pp.713–725, 2021.
- 123) Taheri F., Habibipoor R., Rajabi M." Isolation and molecular identification of endophytic fungi in Saffron (*Crocus sativus* L.)". 12th National and 4th International Biotechnology Congress of the Islamic Republic of Iran, Auhust 22-24, 2021, Iran.
- 124) Thakur R., Singh C., Kaul B."First report of corm rot in *Crocus sativus*". *Indian Phytopathology*, 45, pp. 278, 1992.
- 125) Tian L., Hu S., Wang X., Guo Y., Huang L., Wang L., Li W., "Antagonism of rhizosphere *Streptomyces yangpuensis* CM253 against the pathogenic fungi causing corm rot in saffron (*Crocus sativus* L.)". *Pathogens*, 11, pp.1195, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens11101195>.
- 126) Vafaei S. H., Darvishian E."Etiology of corm rot of saffron in Khorramabad". *Journal of Saffron Research*, 10(2), pp. 294-285, 2022. doi: 10.22077/jsr.2022.5616.1195
- 127) Vardasbi H., Saremi H., Fotouhifar Kh.-B., "Novel endophytic species of *Talaromyces* sect. *Talaromyces* associated with saffron plant to the mycobiota of Iran". *Mycologia Iranica*, 7(2), pp. 219-229, 2020.
- 128) Victorino Í. M. M., Voyron S., Caser M., Orgiazzi A., Demasi S., Berruti A., Scariot V., Bianciotto V., Lumini E. (2021). Metabarcoding of soil fungal communities associated with alpine field-grown

- saffron (*Crocus sativus* L.) inoculated with AM fungi. J. Fungi 7, pp. 45, 2021. doi: 10.3390/jof7010045
- 129) Voglino P. (ed.), " Patologia vegetale. Fanerogame parassite, mixomiceti, bacterii, ifomiceti od eumiceti (funghi)". Unione Tipografico-Editrice (Già Ditta Pombe & C) Torino, Italy, pp. 287, 1905.
- 130) Wani A. M." Studies on corm rot of saffron (*Crocus sativus* L.)", Sher-e-Kashmir University of Agricultural Sciences & Technology of Kashmir, India, pp. 153, 2004.
- 131) Wani Z.A., Ahmad T., Nalli Y." *Porostereum* sp., associated with saffron (*Crocus sativus* L.), is a latent pathogen capable of producing phytotoxic chlorinated aromatic compounds". Curr. Microbiol, 75, pp. 880–887, 2018.
- 132) Wani Z.A., Kumar A., Sultan P., Bindu K., Riyaz-UI Hassan S., Ashraf N." *Mortierella alpina* CS10E4, an oleaginous fungal endophyte of *Crocus sativus* L. enhances apocarotenoid biosynthesis and stress tolerance in the host plant". Sci. Rep., 7, pp. 8598, 2017.
- 133) Wani Z.A., Mirza D.N., Arora P., Riyaz-ul-Hassan S., " Molecular phylogeny, diversity, community structure, and plant growth promoting properties of fungal endophytes associated with corms of saffron plant: An insight into the microbiome of *Crocus sativus* Linn. Fungal Biol., 120, pp.1509–1524, 2016.
- 134) Wei L., Duan X., Lu G., Chang J., Zhou X., Ma H., Qi H., "Identification of saffron corm rot disease pathogen and laboratory screening of chemical agents". Plant Prot., 47, pp.139–145, 2021, doi: 10.16688/j.zwbh.2020521.
- 135) Xu C. X., and Ge Q. X. " A preliminary study on corm rot of *Crocus sativus* L." Acta Agric. Univ. Zhejiangensis. 16, pp. 241–246, 1990.
- 136) Yamamoto W., Omatsu T., Takami K., "Studies on the corm rots of *Crocus sativus* L. I. on saprophytic propagation of *Sclerotinia gladioli* and *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *gladioli* on various plants and soils". Sci. Rep. Hyogo Univ. Agric., 1, pp. 64–70, 1954.
- 137) Yamamoto W., Maeda M., Oyasu N., "Studies on the *Penicillium* diseases occurring on cultivated plants". Scientific reports of the Hyogo University of Agriculture 2, pp. 23–28 (Review of Applied Mycology (1958) 37, 170, 1956.
- 138) Zadoks J. C."Mr. Duhamel's 1728 treatise on the violet root rot of saffron crocus: 'Physical explanation of a disease that perishes several plants in the gastiinois, and saffron in particular Mededelingen". Landbouwhogeschool Wageningen, Nederland, 81-7, 1981.
- 139) Zhang G. H., Zhang X. P., Zhang N. F., He D. Y. "Pathogen identification and drug prevention of *Crocus sativus* corm rot". J. Kaili Univ. 27, pp. 47–49, 2009. doi: 10.3969/j. issn.1673-9329.2009.03.019
- 140) Zhang T., Huang C., Deng C., Zhang Y., Feng Y., Hu J., Wang R., Zhao L., Wang Y., Kai G., "First report of corm rot on saffron caused by *Penicillium solitum* in China". Plant Disease, 104 (2), pp. 579-579, 2020.
- 141) Zheng C-J., Li L., Zou J-P., Han T., Qin L-P., "Identification of a quinazoline alkaloid produced by *Penicillium vinaceum*, an endophytic fungus from *Crocus sativus*, Pharmaceutical Biology, 50:2, pp.129-133, 2012, DOI: 10.3109/13880209.2011.569726
- 142) Zhou S. 2015. Identification and fungicides screening of saffrons rot disease pathogen. Journal of Sichuan University; http://en.cnki.com.cn/Article_en/CJFDTOTAL-SCDX201504036.htm